

Strategic Negotiation Using Facial Emotion Technique

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Abstract

Negotiation occurs daily in different societal levels with affect and emotions taking center stage in negotiation and other motivated performances. Many theories have been put that posit that sufficient information on one's internal affective state is revealed by facial

expression. Contextual emotion hypothesis asserts that facial emotional perception is affected by situational factors. Other's perception of one's facial emotional display could be biased depending on these factors. Based on this hypothesis, one can have different facial displays of the same emotion as this depends on the context in which the emotion is expressed. This paper considers the automatic facial expression analysis problem and aims to propose a technological solution to it far from the traditional experiments and applications in the lab conditions and into the technological analysis in unconstrained conditions. Recent efforts in this direction have shown improvements but how to achieve an accurate, real-time, robust and informative facial expressional analysis still remains vague.

Introduction

Human psychology as a field has extensively studied how facial expressions are perceived and interpreted in terms of health indicators, social signals, and mental emotional models and affective states. A number of theories have come to life to how to encode, represent and interpret facial expressions (Geddes and Linderbaum, 2020). The computer vision community attempted to analyze facial expression by machine analysis but still heavily relied on natural psychology theories and used on convection and coding system.

Negotiation is a daily activity in an adult human's personal and professional lives in the face of strategic and emotionally charged social interaction. Emotion is a crucial part of human factor especially in self relevant and task engaging situations that need cognitive response. Motivated performance situations and their attendant interactions are associated with both positive and negative emotional states of the interactants. To interested partners, negotiations must take the shape of motivated performance.

Organizations must dedicate their energy, money and time to train their front-line employees on good negotiation skills as companies expand internationally in the face of cultural differences (Zhao, Romero and Rudnicky, 2018). Approaching foreign markets needs different methods from those applied in the domestic markets to adequately face the fierce competition to keep a competitive position. Negotiation remains one of the most difficult tasks in management. International negotiation is complex and difficult and affected by cultural and demographic differences making them very costly to enter.

Methodology

Data collection was done through primary and secondary means. The secondary data was obtained by searching through published data. This research used government publications of court cases, journals that touch on strategic negotiation practices and activities, statistical records, and historical documents. The past data collected through the above means, together with online and offline searches were analyzed, reviewed, and interpreted. A systematic literature review was conducted. The report used a scientific electronic library and the Google scholar to locate scholarly publications. Keywords such as facial expressions, strategic

negotiation, and context in emotion were used, to search the articles and paper on the subject matter.

The method of the search was based on publications relevant to the subject matter. The original works and reviews published between 2015 and 2020 were incorporated in the study since they were the most recent established inclusion criteria. Articles that did not fit in the inclusion criteria were dated earlier than 2015 and did not address the topic directly were removed. New materials, websites, and official reports recently published and done in the mentioned area were used, and the data extracted from them were used to update the data in the study. Many of the current literature came upon the topic. Still, it was reduced sizably after analysis of the content of the articles to a good number. The flow was utilized when selecting systematic reviews considered that authors, publication years, study type, objectives, and limitations based on the publications.

There are two sets of data to be included in the study; primary and secondary data that, when triangulated, enhances the quality and outcomes of the research. Primary data were obtained from interviews conducted where two factions are targeted. The interviewees were scholars and learners in this and relevant fields. Structured and unstructured open-ended questions were set and directed to identify respondents. This study was conducted on an 80-person population size that is currently or in the past directly or indirectly involved in managerial roles in organizational negotiation. The sample size was chosen with a marginal error of 0.5% by the use of snowball non-probability sampling. These chain-referrals forms of sampling procedures are useful when referrals are needed, especially when respondents are not easily identifiable and rare for the identification of an unknown potential respondent. The sampling procedure enables the researchers to identify a few likely respondents and approach them for their participation in the study and asking them for further reference or suggesting other potential respondents.

The snowball techniques were identified by Etikan, Alkassim, and Abubakar (2016) and are of three types. The first is the linear in which the researcher is referred by the subject to another one potential respondent making it a line of referrals. The second is an exponential non-discriminative procedure in which respondents give multiple references, and all the numerous referrals are explored before going to the next referral level. The other is an exponential sampling procedure in which the researcher selects one referral and leaves the other. In this procedure, the selected respondent refers the researcher to another reference where the researcher also chooses one. This study used the exponential non-discriminative snowball sampling to achieve the required number of respondents.

Semi-structured questionnaires were used as the preferred data collection tool to compliment the secondary data sources used in the literature review. A questionnaire and critical informant interview were used. Using more than one instrument helps in supplementing information, thus making reliable findings and conclusions. The questionnaire was set to include demographic data of the respondents, the aspects of student tutoring embraced, and the anticipated effects of the engaged approaches

The qualitative part of the data was collected through the use of essential informant interview guides. The guide was be used to facilitate interviews with selected respondents to

support the questionnaire with more information supporting respondents' choices of answers. The interview guide mostly included parts included in the questionnaire but leaving the prompts in an open-ended approach for the clients to give their views about the peer tutoring program.

The instruments were tested based on a small sample of the population. For the questionnaire, five potential respondents were selected to answer the questions. From the five, two will also be interviewed to ascertain the applicability of the tool. Piloting of the instrument was recommended for increasing the validity of the device, and ensuring there were no ambiguous questions. The researchers identified issues that needed reframing as well as eliminating unnecessary parts of the questionnaire. The time required to conduct one interview and the time needed to fill one questionnaire was established during the piloting process of the tools.

Permission was sought from the school and the department of education for granting of authorization/letter for the data collection, after identifying the respondents, the researcher and a few selected research assistants engaged in a physical visit to the identified respondents. Phone-calls were made, and emails were sent to potential respondents requesting the audience to conduct the survey. Once an interview was booked, the researcher took an approximate of 10-15 minutes interviewing and probing the respondent. Some selected respondents were given questionnaires to answer. The researcher gave an allowance of 2 days to collect the questionnaires for the respondents who cite busy schedules.

Secondary data were, therefore, extracted newspaper articles, journals, periodicals, internet sources, and books on negotiation techniques, laws, declarations, and policy instruments, previously researched works, journals, newspapers, magazines, and articles written on the subject under study.

The research objectives guided the data analysis process. The collected information underwent verification before being subjected to the theoretical framework and analyzed through analytical and logical arguments using qualitative approaches. The qualitative information was analyzed through thematic and content analysis before being integrated/triangulated with the primary data findings. Respondents' quotes, views, and ideas were quoted to support the findings and enhance the validity of the results.

The chain-referral sampling procedures were used to identify respondents who led the researcher to others that are unknown but are potential respondents. The researcher were, therefore, be able to locate more respondents, approach them for their participation in the study, and ask them for further referral of more respondents until the required sample size is achieved. The study also adopted a descriptive cross-sectional survey due to its significance in facilitating more comprehensive data sources coverage. Qualitative studies help give succinct and elaborate answers to research problems. The qualitative design used in describing and understanding human behavior, and reading facial expression, while the quantitative approach focuses on the explanation and prediction of human behaviour. The use of both methods, quantitative and qualitative, strengthens the research model as it increases result validity and reliability.

Findings and Conclusion

Negotiators recognize and manage the impact of every situational factor on he process of bargaining and form their perspectives and analyses based on these. It is crucial for negotiators

to fully understand the needs and wants of their counterparts in relations to the subject under negotiation (Shutzberg, 2019). As negotiators face people from different cultures, good communication and listening skills, orientation towards the people's cultural response to communications, the will to use assistance, high self esteem, high aspiration and an attractive personality displayed using facial expression add credence and influence to the negotiators and the organization as a whole. The facial expression technique draws from individual characteristics as opposed to training of the negotiators. The respondents in this study pointed out that they prefer a team of negotiators when negotiating on behalf of a company with an aim of a win-win outcome (Laubert and Parlamis (2019).

The results of the study show that affect in negotiation plays a crucial role as negotiators facing counterparts who expressed anger made concessions easily despite the fact that their counterparts may not have felt the anger in the first place. Those that express anger during negotiations claim more value and also do not lose their ability to create value. Expression of emotions influences the social interference of the counterpart and their subsequent behavior during negotiation.

On the other hand, expression of positive emotions helps increase the willingness of the counterpart to agree to proposals and view things in a better light. Positive facial expression of emotions is a useful strategy but has to be carefully added with negative emotions for successful negotiation and goal achievement (Zhao, Romero and Rudnicky, 2018). This implies that facial expression of anger and emotions in negotiation plays the role of a both negotiation skills and negotiation strategy. This implies that it is crucial, for organizations to train their front-line employees such as marketers and deal-makers on building powerful negotiation skills with facial expression technique taking center stage for a better deal making and leadership.

References

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